

autoFISH: construction of the fluidics system

Short name: autofish_fluidics-construction

Version: v3

Date: 1.3.2026

Abstract: This custom-built fluidic system is based on a published paper for merFISH and ORCA (Moffitt JR et al., 2016), but it has some modified components, as specified below. The main changes are

- **Bubble trap** to remove air bubbles
- **Flow sensor** to measure pumped volume after each step, and stop the system in case a problem occurs
- **Pump placement** in the middle of the fluidics circuit. While it draws liquid from the different reservoirs, it pushes it through both the bubble trap and the imaging chamber. We found that this has several advantages:
 - Reduces air in the system.
 - Permits the efficient use of the bubble trap.
 - Reduces the movement of the coverslip when the pump is activated → Reduces the risk of loss of focus.
 - Combined use of a computer-controlled valve and plate robot: syringes for general-purpose buffers, 96-well plates for round-specific buffers.

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1 Building the system

1.1 Recommended installation workflow

1. Drivers are often required for the computer to communicate with its various components. If communication is not possible, missing drivers are frequently an issue.
 - a. **Serial-to-USB adaptors** are needed to connect the pump and valve, which have serial ports, to the computer's USB ports. Windows recognizes some adaptors and installs the drivers automatically; for others, they must be installed manually.
 - b. **CNC robot:** The driver is not installed automatically, and manual installation is required (more details are provided in the robot section).
2. Install **control software autoFISH** (<https://github.com/fish-quant/autofish>).
3. Ensure **all required components can be controlled from Python** (we provide dedicated test scripts [here](#)). For new components, a new Python class must be added.
4. Perform **test runs** without liquid and tubing to ensure communication is working and to familiarize yourself with the control software.
5. Once all components are controlled, start **adding the fluidic connections**

1.2 Tubing

We use either **TEFZEL/ETFE** or **PTFE** tubing with a small inner diameter (ID =0.5mm = 0.020") to minimize the amount of required liquid. The other diameter (OD) of 1/16" is standard for many fluidics applications.

1.3 Used connectors

P-658	1/4-28 Female to Female Luer	Connects on syringe (male Luer) and connects to XP-202	
XP-202	Flangeless Fitting Delrin, 1/4-28 Flat-Bottom For 1/16" OD	Connect tubing to a threaded 1/4-28 Port.	
P-655	Luer Adapter Assembly 1/4-28 Female to Male Luer	Connects to output of valve (female Luer) allows attachment of XP-202	
P-646	Barbed to Threaded Male for soft 1/16" ID tubing, 1/4-28 male	To connect soft tubing (imaging chamber)	
P-603	Standard Union Delrin, 1/4-28 Port	Screws on IDEX P-646 and allows connection of XP-202	
P-692	Conical adaptor for soft tubing, 1/4-28 male.	To connect soft tubing (vacuum pump)	

1.4 Typical connections

Several connectors are used to connect the tubing to the different components. The connectors are indicated **in blue**. The images below show the assembly of the two main connection types:

Most connections rely on a standard <u>1/4-28 Threaded Connection</u> , where you use nut (blue) and a threaded connector (red) to connect the tube with another connector	
Other connections are based on <u>male or female Luer locks</u> (common on syringes). A Luer connector can be used in combination with a threaded connection to connect fluidics tubing to a syringe.	

2 Components

Here, we describe the process of building the system, starting with buffer storage and concluding with the flow sensor. Please refer to the dedicated section for a comprehensive list of all required components.

Component list.

2.1 Buffer storage 1: liquid handling robot

We used a 3D milling machine, replacing the spindle with a custom-printed syringe holder. We also used Plexiglas with cutouts for 96-well plates.

⚠ A driver is needed to communicate with the robot. Suppose Windows does not install it automatically when you connect the robot to the computer for the first time. In that case, you will need to download the Driver (usually provided by the company) and install it yourself. If not provided, they are usually the drivers required to communicate with an Arduino (see [here](#) for some instructions).

- **Model:** GRBL 3018 or similar
- **Important:** Controlled by **GRBL**
- **Hamilton needle**
- **Connection:** **IDEX P-655 and P-202**

Note: we glued the connectors together, since they can wiggle free when the robot moves a lot.

2.1.1 Needle holder

We 3d-printed a needle holder that fits in the spindle holder. This is essentially a cylinder with a central hole to accommodate the needle.

We further added a headless screw that can be used to secure the needle firmly.

2.1.2 96 well-plate holder

To securely place the 96 well plates on the robot (example on the left for a 3018 robot with plate dimension of 30x18cm), we use a holder made of sturdy cardboard or Plexiglas.

2.1.3 Construction and testing of the robot

1. Build according to instructions. Once built, you should be able to control the robot using the provided joystick.
2. Install the provided driver (for our robot, it was named CH340SER.exe)

3. Connect the USB cable to the computer.
4. Determine your Machine's COM port (see [below](#)).
5. Open provided control software (for our robot `grblControl`)
6. Attempt to move the robot from within the software.
7. You should now be able to use the robot in our Python control software.

2.2 Buffer storage 2: syringe holder

For general buffers, e.g. for washing or imaging, we use syringes with a female Luer lock. We use a modular syringe Holder from Warner instruments permitting to assemble a syringe holder accepting different volumes, as well as the corresponding Support Stand (**W3 64-0162**).

Connection: [P-658](#) and [XP-202](#)

When the system is not used, we wash all fluidic lines with water and remove the syringes. We close the connectors (P-658) with a lid (the ones shown on the right come from a purification kit and are used to close purification columns).

2.3 Automated valve

We use computer-controlled valves with multiple inputs (eight for the one listed below) and a single output. Several companies produce such valves; we use **Hamilton** or **AMF**.

Shown on the right is a Hamilton valve with 5 connected inputs (ports 2 to 6) and one output. **Inputs** are connected with threaded connections; **output** is connected with a female Luer.

- **Entry:** [IDEX XP-202](#)
- **Exit (Only Hamilton):** [IDEX P-655 + XP-202](#)

2.3.1 Input/output valve

Certain valves permit flow in both directions. Thus, they can either be used to select from several incoming fluidic lines, e.g., to choose from different buffers, or to select for different output lines, e.g., to direct a buffer to a specific sample. We use the latter when working with Ibidi multi-channel slides. Our control software, `autoFISH`, supports both input and outlet valves.

2.3.2 Hamilton MVP/4 valve

For Hamilton, the valve positioner and the valve itself are required. The valve positioner is delivered with a power supply and control cable.

⚠ To **communicate correctly** with the valve, the address and DIP switch must be set before use.

Address switches

The address switch is set such that the MVP/4 valve is set to "0"

DIP and termination switches

- DIP switches (4-6): used valve has 8 ports (Table 2-2, page 14).
- Termination switch (7-8): indicate that only one valve is connected

SWITCH	4	5	6	7	8
State	ON	ON	OFF	ON	OFF

2.4 Peristaltic Pump

Currently, supported pumps are

- **Ismatec REGLO DIGITAL**
- **Longer BT100.**
- Needs to be controllable via the serial port.
- **Entry & exit: Blunt Gauge 25 needles (OD 0.54mm) with Luer Lock. + P-655 + XP-202**

2.5 Bubble trap with vacuum pump

We use a **bubble trap** to remove air bubbles from the buffers (especially when EC is degassing). The bubble trap can be connected to a **vacuum pump**, which will help increase bubble removal. To create a vacuum, we use a small piezo pump. The pump itself is very cheap, and the controller is comparatively expensive, but it is very convenient. The starter set listed in the components section contains the vacuum pump, controller, and soft-wall tubing.

Shown on the left is the bubble trap with the entry/exit of the fluidics on the top, and the vacuum line connected at the bottom.

- **Target flow rate:** 4 ml / min (sine signal, 250V, 50 HZ)
More settings see below.
- **Connection of fluidics:** XP-202
- **Connection of vacuum line:** P-692 + soft tubing

Target flow rate	Amplitude	Frequency		Target flow rate	Amplitude	Frequency
7 ml/min	250 V	100-110 Hz		2 ml/min	220-240 V	20 Hz
6 ml/min	250 V	80-90 Hz		1 ml/min	125-135 V	20 Hz
5 ml/min	250 V	55-65 Hz		0,5 ml/min	90-100 V	15 Hz
4 ml/min	250 V	40-50 Hz		0,25 ml/min	85-95 V	8 Hz
3 ml/min	250 V	30-35 Hz		0,1 ml/min	80-90 V	3 Hz

As a general guideline the amplitude should be kept as high as possible while varying the frequency.

2.6 Flow sensor

We use a flow sensor from Sensirion. The proposed evaluation kit comes with a USB cable that permits measuring flow with a **provided viewer software (USB/RS485)**. Measured flow can be saved in a csv file, which can be read by the Python control software.

- **Entry and exit:** [XP-202](#)

2.7 Imaging chambers

2.7.1 BIOPTTECHS FCS2

We use the Bioptechs FCS2 flow chamber for imaging of tissue samples. We recommend purchasing the starter set, which also contains the temperature control and several silicon gaskets.

Show on the left is the mounted chamber, with the fluidics entry on the right, exit on the left. Temperature control is connected on the top.

- **Entry:** soft tubing + IDEX P-646 + IDEX P-603 + XP-202

- **Exit:** only the soft tubing without connectors to avoid clogging when parts of the samples dislodge.

2.7.2 Ibidi multi-channel slides

The advantage of these multi-channel slides is that multiple conditions can be tested in parallel, e.g., control vs drug treatment. They can be connected with an elbow Luer adaptor sold by Ibidi. We found that softwall tubing (TYGON LMT-55, ID 1.52mm) can be used to connect with the more rigid tubing used in the fluidics system.

Important considerations

- We found it difficult to obtain consistent flow rates across channels when using a manifold to distribute liquid. Therefore, we use an **automated outlet valve** to flow liquid subsequently through each channel. This leads to only a marginal increase in experimental duration since flow duration is the longest only for the first channel, where the entire system is filled. For subsequent channels, a shorter duration is required because only the liquid between the valve and the channel needs to be replaced.
- To **avoid air bubbles** when connecting the Luer locks to the channel slide, we recommend filling the slide completely and gently pressing the Luer lock inside to displace the extra liquid.
- For temperature control, we use the chamber slides in a small top-stage incubator, e.g., an Okolab unit.

- Imaging multiple channels means **moving the objective over larger distances**, which can be problematic regarding loss of focus and immersion medium.
- Ideally, the system should be equipped with an autofocus.
- High-NA water objectives with an automated water dispenser can help maintain immersion; otherwise, generously covering the underside of the channel slide with oil can also help.

2.8 TTL trigger with Arduino

In our control software, we provide the option to communicate with a microscope via TTL pulses.

1. A **TTL OUT** sent from the Arduino to the microscope indicates that an acquisition should be launched.
2. The Arduino then waits for an incoming TTL (**TTL IN**) coming from the microscope to indicate that the acquisition is terminated, and that the next fluidic round can be started/

An easy way to send and receive such triggers is by using an Arduino. Arduinos are easy to build, provide a convenient programming interface, and can be tested using Python code.

2.8.1 Building the Arduino

Instructions are provided for an **Arduino UNO R3**. Other options might work as well, but were not tested. Upload the software to your Arduino (<https://docs.arduino.cc/learn/starting-guide/getting-started-arduino/>).

1. Upload program. For this, we use the Arduino IDE (<https://www.arduino.cc/en/software/>)
 - a. Open Arduino IDE.
 - b. Connect Arduino via the USB cable (no power cord needed).
 - c. Select the SKETCHBOOK item from the menu on the left.
 - d. Click on 'NEW SKETCH' at the bottom.
 - e. This will open a new window.
 - f. Select your Arduino from the pulldown menu (Step 1, screenshot below).
 - g. Get the code that should be running on the Arduino by going to https://github.com/fish-quant/autofish/blob/main/autofish/Arduino_TTL_sync/Arduino_TTL_sync.ino and selecting the code shown in the editor.
 - h. Paste this code in the SKETCHBOOK window.
 - i. Press the UPLOAD button in the upper part of the window (Step 2, screenshot below).

2. Create TTL lines on the Arduino: Create two TTL lines, with a shared ground. As an end connector, we use BMC (male or female, depending on the needs)

TTL OUT:	+ connected to pin 12	- to (shared) GND	Blue below
TTL IN:	+ connected to pin10	- to (shared) GND	Black below

2.8.2 Testing the Arduino

The provided code sets two additional pins: **pin 7 is HIGH** and **pin 8 is LOW**. These pins allow the simulation of the incoming TTL signal to indicate that the acquisition is done.

Connection of TTL out to a LED for testing.

Connection of TTL to the pin 7/8 for testing

1. **Connect the TTLS**
 - a. **TTL OUT** to a small test circuit with an LED (e.g., as described here: <https://docs.arduino.cc/built-in-examples/basics/Blink/>)
Note: LEDs have longer and shorter end, the longer one goes to the +.
 - b. **TTL IN:** - to the GND, + to pin 8
2. Identify the **COM port** to which the Arduino is connected.
3. Launch Python code (`arduino_TTL_synchronization.py`), provided on GitHub: <https://github.com/fish-quant/autofish/tree/main/hardware-tests>
 - a. Update port in serial connection: `arduino=serial.Serial ...`
 - b. Launch the While loop.
 - c. You will be asked for user input. `start` will send the TTL OUT, and the LED should turn on and remain on. There is also small LED on the Arduino that will turn on.
 - d. To indicate the acquisition is done, set the TTL to HIGH (by moving to pin 7). The LEDs should turn off.

3 Component list

Note: We listed the minimum number of IDEX connectors you will need, so ordering a few extra for security might be good.

Component	References / Comments	Quantity
Peristaltic pump	Has to be controllable via serial port. Supported are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ismatec REGLO DIGITAL or • Longer BT100 	1
Tubing for Peristaltic pump	We replace the tubing on a regular basis to guarantee constant flow rates.	Multiple
Tubing (fluidics)	Tube TEFZEL/ETFE 1/16" (OD) x 0.50mm (ID)	5m
Clear PVC tubing	McMasterCarr 5233K51. ID1/16" ID To connect the imaging chamber	1m
Tubing to threaded port	IDEX XP-202	20
Syringe adapter	IDEX P-658	1 per syringe, 1 for Hamilton valve
Male Luer	IDEX P-655	2
Barbed to threaded Male	IDEX P-646	1
Standard Union for threaded ports	IDEX P-603	1
Conical to threaded male	IDEX P-692	1
	LIDS for closing when done	
Syringe holder	Warner Instruments : stand, base unit, additional units	1
Robot	CNC 3018 or similar (Important to have GRBL support). These robots are available from different providers (e.g. Genmitsu, SainSmart). We recommend the more expensive versions made from metal with emergency stop, limit switches and manual adjustment screws	1
Needles	Hamilton™ 90523 (Kel F Hub Needles) Ga25 (ID 0.26mm), needle style 3 (blunt), 51mm	1 (sold by 6)
Imaging chamber	BIOPTECHS FCS2 Starter set	1
Valve positioner	Hamilton MVP/4 Valve Positioner	1
Valve	Computer controlled valve(s). Available from different providers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AMF Microfluidic rotary valve RVM fast: • Hamilton: Hamilton CERAMIC, HVCX, 8-5; Requires also valve positioner: Hamilton MVP/4 Valve Positioner 	1 or 2 (if distribution valve is used as well).
Flow sensor	Sensirion Flow Sensor evaluation kit SLF3S-0600	1
Bubble trap	ELVEFLOW Autoclavable Bubble Trap for Microfluidics. We usually use the small volume version (20-30 ul).	1
Vacuum pump + control	Bartels mp-Lab! Evaluation Set	1
Serial-to-USB adaptor	USB to Straight-Through RS232 Serial Adapter	2

4 Serial port control

4.1 Find the COM for connected components

For each connected component, you must know the **COM port**. This port usually doesn't change. To see on which port your components are

1. Right-click on the Windows Start Icon and select "Device Manager."
2. Open the "Ports (COM & LPT)" section.
3. Locate the appropriate Device (if you don't know which one, disconnect and reconnect it) and note which COM port it is connected to.

4.2 Test already defined components

In autoFISH, we support components from different providers. We provide separate Python test codes for each.

4.3 Serial command testing for new components

Dedicated programs can send commands to serial ports to test the new hardware component.

- **Termite**: simple program to send and receive data to a USB port (https://www.compuphase.com/software_termite.htm)
- **Portmon**: a tool to monitor activity on serial ports <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/sysinternals/downloads/portmon>
- Some more information on how to **monitor serial port activity** <https://technet.microsoft.com/en-us/sysinternals/bb896644>

Once this works, you can use our Python control software `autoFISH`. Here, you will need to write a new class in `automator.py` that integrates the specific commands for your component.

5 Version history and archiving

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
v1	31.10.2014	Mueller F	Initial version.
v2	10.1.2025	Mueller F	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.
V3	1.3.2026	Mueller F	Add Ibidi multi-channel slides.